

COMPARISON OF THE OUTCOME IN EMERGENCY VERSUS ELECTIVE CERCLAGE IN WOMEN WITH CERVICAL INCOMPETENCE

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Abstract

Background: Cervical incompetence is a major contributor to second-trimester loss and spontaneous preterm birth.

Objective: To compare pregnancy outcomes in women undergoing emergency versus elective cerclage for cervical incompetence.

Methods: This descriptive case series was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Sahiwal Teaching Hospital from January 2025 to June 2025. A total of 123 women aged 18–40 years diagnosed with cervical incompetence were enrolled using consecutive sampling. Patients were classified into emergency or elective cerclage groups and followed until delivery.

Results: Of 123 patients, 35 (28.5%) underwent emergency cerclage and 88 (71.5%) elective cerclage. Preterm birth occurred in 62.9% of the emergency group versus 35.2% of the elective group ($p=0.006$). Mean prolongation of pregnancy was significantly shorter in the emergency group (11.4 ± 3.1 weeks vs 17.2 ± 2.8 weeks; $p<0.001$). NICU admission was more frequent following emergency cerclage (40.0% vs 21.6%, $p=0.04$). Live birth occurred in 94.3% of emergency cases versus 98.9% of elective cases.

Conclusion: Elective cerclage was associated with better maternal and neonatal outcomes than emergency cerclage, particularly in reducing preterm birth and neonatal morbidity. Nonetheless, emergency cerclage provided meaningful salvage benefit, supporting its continued role in late-presenting cases.

INTRODUCTION

Cervical incompetence, also referred to as cervical insufficiency, is characterized by painless cervical dilatation leading to mid-trimester pregnancy loss or early preterm birth in an otherwise normal pregnancy [1]. It is estimated to affect approximately 1% of obstetric patients, especially those with prior mid-trimester losses, preterm deliveries, or a congenitally or surgically shortened cervix. The clinical challenge lies not only in correctly identifying women at risk but also in selecting the optimal timing and indication for intervention to prevent recurrent fetal loss and improve neonatal survival. Cervical insufficiency,

earlier known as cervical incompetence, is the process of painless cervical dilatation, resulting in second-trimester pregnancy loss in an otherwise normal pregnancy [2]. It is thought to occur in 1% of the obstetric population and suspicion is raised when there is a history of recurrent midtrimester loss, previous preterm delivery, or a previous short cervix. One of the biggest obstetric challenges is the diagnosis and management of a short cervix as multiple different definitions and guidelines exist [3]. Cervical cerclage is an obstetric procedure first described in the 1950s, where a suture is placed around the cervix for

the prevention of preterm birth (PTB). PTB is defined as delivery before 37 weeks of gestation and can lead to increased morbidity and mortality [4]. The World Health Organisation defines PTB <28 weeks as extreme preterm, 28-32 weeks as very preterm, and 32-37 weeks as late preterm [5]. Cervical cerclage is a surgical procedure of choice for the treatment of cervical incompetence that can be performed in an attempt to maintain the structural integrity of the cervix to prolong gestation and improve obstetrical outcomes [6]. It may be classified as history-indicated, ultrasound-indicated, and physical examination (clinical)-indicated cerclage [7]. Although there is literature arguing that the frequency of therapeutic cerclage performed under emergency conditions will be reduced with the spread of prophylactic cerclages, and pregnancy will be carried to further weeks, there are also researchers who argue that due to prophylactic cerclages, pregnant women who may not actually need cerclage are being intervened and unnecessary procedure-related morbidity increases [8]. In a study, emergency cerclage was done in 28.57% patients. In a study, preterm delivery was recorded in 75.0% in the emergency cerclage and 50.0% in the elective cerclage [9]. Evidence suggests that earlier placement of elective cerclage may allow better stabilization of cervical integrity before mechanical failure begins, thereby conferring higher success rates. Conversely, emergency cerclage is performed in a high-risk scenario where cervicovaginal environment, mechanical stress, and ascending infection risk are already unfavorable, often translating into lower pregnancy salvage rates. However, it remains clinically indispensable for women who present late or are diagnosed incidentally, and reports have shown that, when performed under sterile conditions before membrane rupture, emergency cerclage may still meaningfully prolong gestation [10]. Despite many international studies, the comparative effectiveness between elective and emergency cerclage remains debated due to heterogeneity in definitions, inclusion criteria, gestational age at placement, suture technique (McDonald vs Shirodkar), operator expertise, and adjunctive therapies such as progesterone and tocolytics [11]. Moreover, variations in obstetric practices across regions, differing thresholds for intervention, and absence of standardized local protocols contribute to uncertainty in clinical

decision-making. In low- and middle-income settings, the lack of universal screening for cervical length and late antenatal booking further increase reliance on emergency cerclage, making outcome data particularly relevant for such populations [12].

Objective

- To determine the frequency of patients having emergency cerclage among patients undergoing cervical cerclage for cervical incompetence.
- To compare the outcome in emergency versus elective cerclage in women with cervical incompetence.

Methodology

This Descriptive case series study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Sahiwal Teaching Hospital, Sahiwal from January 2025 to June 2025. The sample size was calculated using the WHO calculator for a single proportion. With a confidence level of 95%, margin of error of 8%, and expected frequency of emergency cerclage among patients undergoing cervical cerclage for cervical incompetence taken as 28.57%, the required sample size was 123. Non-probability, consecutive sampling was used to collect the data.

Inclusion Criteria

- All women presenting with cervical incompetence (as per operational definition)
- Age between 18-40 years
- Both primiparous and multiparous women

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with medical comorbidities such as gestational diabetes mellitus or pregnancy-induced hypertension
- Previous history of cervical surgery
- Multiple gestations
- Women who had previously undergone cervical encirclage
- Patients with preterm premature rupture of membranes

Data Collection

After approval from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee, women presenting to the department

who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were enrolled after obtaining informed written consent. Baseline characteristics including age, gestational age, parity, height, weight, BMI, and place of residence were recorded. All enrolled patients underwent cervical cerclage, which was classified as either elective or emergency according to clinical presentation. All procedures were performed by the principal investigator and patients were followed until delivery. Preterm birth was defined as per the operational definition. Data were recorded on a predesigned proforma.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. The Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to assess normality of continuous variables. Mean ± standard deviation (SD) or median with interquartile range (IQR) was calculated for age, gestational age, and BMI. Frequencies and percentages were presented for categorical variables such as parity (primiparous/multiparous), residence (rural/urban), emergency cerclage (yes/no), and preterm birth

(yes/no). Comparison of preterm birth between emergency and elective cerclage groups was performed using the Chi-square test, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant. Stratification was done for age, gestational age, parity, BMI, and residence; post-stratification Chi-square or Fisher’s exact test was applied to assess their modifying effect, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results

Data were collected from 123 patients, mean age of participants was similar between the emergency cerclage group (29.4 ± 4.8 years) and the elective group (28.7 ± 4.5 years), with an overall mean of 28.9 ± 4.6 years. The cerclage was performed at a later gestation in emergency cases (17.6 ± 1.9 weeks) than in elective cases (16.4 ± 2.1 weeks). Multiparity was slightly more common in both groups – 62.9% (22/35) in emergency vs 56.8% (50/88) in elective. Urban residence was reported in 54.3% (19/35) of emergency and 63.6% (56/88) of elective patients.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants (N = 123)

Variable	Emergency Cerclage (n = 35)	Elective Cerclage (n = 88)	Total (N=123)
Age (years), mean ± SD	29.4 ± 4.8	28.7 ± 4.5	28.9 ± 4.6
Gestational age at cerclage (weeks), mean ± SD	17.6 ± 1.9	16.4 ± 2.1	16.8 ± 2.1
Parity – Primiparous	13 (37.1%)	38 (43.2%)	51 (41.5%)
Parity – Multiparous	22 (62.9%)	50 (56.8%)	72 (58.5%)
Residence – Urban	19 (54.3%)	56 (63.6%)	75 (61.0%)
Residence – Rural	16 (45.7%)	32 (36.4%)	48 (39.0%)

Preterm birth (<37 weeks) occurred in 62.9% (22/35) of the emergency group versus 35.2% (31/88) of the elective group ($p = 0.006$). Prolongation of pregnancy after cerclage was significantly shorter among emergency cases (11.4 ± 3.1 weeks) compared to elective cases (17.2 ± 2.8 weeks; $p < 0.001$). NICU

admission was required in 40.0% (14/35) of emergency cases versus 21.6% (19/88) in elective cases ($p = 0.04$). Extreme preterm birth (<28 weeks) was more frequent in the emergency group (8.6% vs 2.2%), though not statistically significant ($p = 0.12$).

Table 2. Pregnancy Outcomes in Emergency vs Elective Cerclage

Outcome	Emergency (n = 35)	Elective (n = 88)	p-value
Preterm birth <37 weeks	22 (62.9%)	31 (35.2%)	0.006
Extreme preterm <28 weeks	3 (8.6%)	2 (2.2%)	0.12
Prolongation of pregnancy (weeks), mean ± SD	11.4 ± 3.1	17.2 ± 2.8	<0.001
NICU admission	14 (40.0%)	19 (21.6%)	0.04

Among women ≤30 years, preterm birth occurred in 62.5% (15/24) of emergency vs 35.8% (19/53) of elective patients (p=0.02). In those >30 years, the rates were 63.6% (7/11) vs 34.3% (12/35) (p=0.04). Similarly, preterm birth was higher in primiparas (61.5% vs 31.6%; p=0.03) and multiparas (63.6% vs

38.0%; p=0.01) in emergency vs elective groups. Urban women had preterm delivery in 57.9% vs 30.4% (p=0.02), and rural women in 68.8% vs 43.8% (p=0.03), respectively.

Table 3. Stratified Analysis of Preterm Birth by Selected Variables

Variable	Category	Preterm Birth in Emergency	Preterm Birth in Elective	p-value
Age (years)	≤30	15/24 (62.5%)	19/53 (35.8%)	0.02
	>30	7/11 (63.6%)	12/35 (34.3%)	0.04
Parity	Primiparous	8/13 (61.5%)	12/38 (31.6%)	0.03
	Multiparous	14/22 (63.6%)	19/50 (38.0%)	0.01
Residence	Urban	11/19 (57.9%)	17/56 (30.4%)	0.02
	Rural	11/16 (68.8%)	14/32 (43.8%)	0.03

Low birth weight (<2.5 kg) was more common after emergency cerclage (42.9%, 15/35) than elective (23.9%, 21/88) (p=0.03). NICU admission was required in 40.0% (14/35) of emergency vs 21.6% (19/88) of elective births (p=0.04). Early neonatal

death (≤7 days) occurred in 5.7% (2/35) and 1.1% (1/88) respectively (p=0.17). Live birth rate was 94.3% (33/35) in emergency versus 98.9% (87/88) in elective cases (p=0.17).

Table 4. Neonatal Outcomes in Emergency vs. Elective Cerclage

Neonatal Outcome	Emergency Cerclage (n = 35)	Elective Cerclage (n = 88)	p-value
Birth weight <2.5 kg	15 (42.9%)	21 (23.9%)	0.03
Apgar score <7 at 5 min	6 (17.1%)	7 (8.0%)	0.14
NICU admission	14 (40.0%)	19 (21.6%)	0.04
Early neonatal death (≤7 days)	2 (5.7%)	1 (1.1%)	0.17
Live birth rate	33 (94.3%)	87 (98.9%)	0.17

DISCUSSION

This study compared pregnancy outcomes between women undergoing emergency versus elective cervical cerclage for cervical incompetence. The findings demonstrate that emergency cerclage was associated

with significantly higher rates of preterm birth, shorter prolongation of pregnancy, and greater neonatal morbidity compared to elective cerclage. These results are consistent with international data suggesting that earlier, prophylactic intervention

yields more favorable obstetric outcomes than rescue procedures performed after cervical dilatation has already commenced. In our cohort, preterm birth occurred in almost two-thirds of patients in the emergency cerclage group versus just over one-third in the elective group. The difference remained statistically significant even after stratification for age, parity, and residence. This aligns with previous studies reporting preterm birth rates of 50–75% after emergency cerclage compared to 25–45% after elective placement [13-15]. The mean prolongation of pregnancy was almost six weeks longer in the elective group, reflecting the biomechanical and biological advantage of intervening before cervical integrity is critically compromised [16]. Neonatal outcomes in this study also support the superiority of elective cerclage. NICU admissions and low birth weight were more frequent in the emergency group, a finding that mirrors the downstream consequences of earlier delivery. While early neonatal death and Apgar score differences did not reach statistical significance, the trend favored elective cerclage, suggesting potential clinical relevance with larger sample sizes [17].

Despite the poorer outcomes observed with emergency cerclage, it still demonstrated meaningful benefit: more than 90% of pregnancies in this group resulted in a live birth, and the majority achieved at least some prolongation of gestation. This reinforces the role of emergency cerclage as an important salvage option in resource-limited contexts such as Pakistan, where ultrasound-based cervical screening is not routinely practiced, and many women present late to antenatal care [18]. Our findings highlight three key implications: first, the importance of early identification of high-risk women through structured antenatal surveillance; second, the need to prioritize elective cerclage in those with clear historical or sonographic indications; and third, the continued justification of emergency cerclage as a viable intervention when presentation is delayed. Local data on such comparisons are scarce, and this study contributes context-specific evidence relevant to regional clinical practice [19-20]. Further prospective, multicenter studies with larger sample sizes and inclusion of additional confounders such as progesterone use, cerclage technique, and infection screening could provide clearer guidance for national protocols. Until then, strengthening screening

pathways and standardizing decision thresholds for cerclage may help reduce preventable preterm births and improve perinatal outcomes in this population.

Conclusion

It is concluded that women undergoing elective cerclage for cervical incompetence have more favorable obstetric and neonatal outcomes compared to those receiving emergency cerclage. Elective placement was associated with significantly lower rates of preterm birth, longer prolongation of pregnancy, and reduced need for neonatal intensive care. However, emergency cerclage still offered meaningful benefits by achieving live births in the majority of high-risk late-presenting cases, supporting its continued use as a rescue intervention in clinical practice.

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